

EXPRESSION OF QUANTITATIVE IN UZBEKI AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article describes the expression of quantification in Uzbek and English languages, syntactic and grammatical analysis of quantitative units. Similar and different aspects of quantitative units in Uzbek and English usage are compared.

Key words: language levels, quantification, comparative level, singular form, counting numerical words.

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ КОЛИЧЕСТВЕННОГО В УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается выражение квантификации в узбекском и английском языках, синтаксический и грамматический разбор количественных единиц. Сравниваются сходные и различные аспекты использования количественных единиц в узбекском и английском языках.

Ключевые слова: языковые уровни, квантификация, сравнительный уровень, форма единственного числа, счетные числовые слова.

INTRODUCTION

Quantitativeness is considered one of the most common and important classifiers among language levels in the world. The quantitative sign can be used as an important factor in distinguishing units of a certain level or in defining similarities and differences between units of comparable levels.

Quantitative means units representing quantity and this system is of special importance in various developed languages, as well as in Uzbek, with its specific features. We can find the first ideas about quantitative units in the work of the scientist Mahmud Koshgari, who worked in many fields of linguistics in our country, "Devonu Lug'at Turk". Comparing the expression of sin in verbs with Arabic, the scientist emphasizes that Turkish languages do not distinguish between dual and plural, and the number is divided into 2 opposite groups: singular and plural forms, and explains his opinion with many arguments.

On the basis of Mahmud Koshgari's ideas, units representing quantity are being formed in the modern Uzbek language.

Quantitative units represented by the number word group are divided into several groups:

1. Counting numbers - one, two, three. (bir, ikki, uch);
2. Number of pieces - one, two. (bitta, ikkita);
3. Conjectural numbers - tens, hundreds. (o'ntacha, yuzlab);
4. Cumulative numbers - two, three. (ikkiovlon, uchala);
5. Fractional numbers - half, one tenth. (yarim, o'ndan bir).

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Quantitative units represented by nouns are called "calculation numerals". In our region, such units originally belong to the noun group, but when they come together with numbers, they become its component and express quantity.

They include:

1. Computational words indicating a fragment of the whole; a piece of watermelon, a slice of melon, a loaf of bread. (bir karch tarvuz, bir tilik qovun, bir burda non);
2. Counting words indicating the totality of the subject; a herd of horses, a herd of sheep. (bir uyur ot, bir qo'ra qo'y);
3. Calculation words indicating length; a mile, a yard, a yard. (chaqirim, yig'och, qarich);
4. Time measuring words; seconds, minutes, hours, days. (soniya, daqiqa, soat, sutka);
5. Value words; penny, coin. (miri, tiyin, tanga);

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When we compare the quantitative signs of the Uzbek language with the English language, it is possible to observe the similar and, at the same time, different aspects. The similar signs of units expressing quantity in these 2 languages are simply that the words expressing quantity in English are added before the noun group, like Uzbek, and are expressed as follows:

- 1. Much and little are used to express the number of uncountable nouns.
- 2. Many and few are used with plural nouns.
- 3. A lot of/ lots of/ plenty of is used with uncountable and plural nouns.
- 4. Much and many are mainly used in negative and interrogative sentences. A lot(of) is used in sentences.

All of the above-mentioned quantitative units represent the amount of a certain thing, but they have different aspects according to their usage and grammatical form.

In Uzbek and English, quantitative relationships are also expressed using morphemes. Quantity is also expressed in nouns by adding -s in Uzbek, and -s in English. In the Uzbek language, we can include all adverbial adverbs in morphemes expressing quantity, but this feature is not reflected in the English language. The linguist scientist A. Ghulomov gives extensive and detailed information about the plural forms of verbs. Since the scientist's views on the plural category in the Uzbek language have been described in this research, no attitude has been expressed about the singular form of demonstrative adverbs. But as the opposite of that plurality, we can take singular forms of morphemes representing quantity.

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